

N- α -Pyridyl-N'-Benzoyl Thiourea as a Chelating Agent for the Determination of Rhodium

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N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea is a useful chelating agent for the gravimetric as well as spectrophotometric determination of rhodium(III). The metal chelate is precipitated in the pH range of 3.5 to 5.5 and can be weighed as $\text{Rh}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{OS})_3$. Rhodium(III) is determined gravimetrically with the thio-ligand in presence of palladium(II), platinum(IV), iridium(IV), osmium(VI), ruthenium(III) and commonly associated base metals by the use of masking agents or controlling the acidity of the solution.

The light brown chelate formed by rhodium with N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea can be extracted quantitatively with chloroform in the pH range 5.24-6.3 in presence of ethanol. The extract obeys Beer's law at 360 nm over the concentration ranging from 0.69 $\mu\text{g Rh ml}^{-1}$ to 6.9 $\mu\text{g Rh ml}^{-1}$. The colour of the extract is stable for 24 hours. It is possible to determine microgram quantities of rhodium(III) spectrophotometrically using N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea as a colour forming reagent in presence of most of base metals and all other platinum metals. The sensitivity of the colour reaction and the molar absorptivity of the complex are 0.0102 $\mu\text{g Rh cm}^{-2}$ and $9.54 \times 10^3 \text{ l.mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. Cyanide ion, however, interferes with the spectrophotometry of the metal.

None of the organic thio compounds which were employed by earlier investigators¹⁻⁷, can be recommended for either gravimetric or spectrophotometric determination of rhodium. N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea (PBT) was used by Shome and co-workers⁸ as a chelating agent for the determination of osmium(VI). In the present work PBT is employed for the gravimetry and spectrophotometry of rhodium(III). Rhodium(III) forms a light-brown complex with the thio-ligand which can be weighed as $\text{Rh}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{OS})_3$. The metal can be precipitated with PBT in presence of commonly associated base metals using suitable masking agents. It is separated from other platinum metals by either adjusting the acidity of the solution or prior reduction of the interfering ions. Iridium(IV), however, does not affect this determination. The rhodium chelate is soluble in common organic solvents and can be extracted with a mixture of ethanol and chloroform to produce a yellowish brown solution. The extract obeys Beer's law at 360 nm. The colour of the extract is stable for more than 24 hrs. Rhodium is separated from various foreign ions by extraction and subsequently determined spectrophotometrically.

Experimental

Apparatus: A Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer, PMQ-II model with 1 cm quartz cells, was used for the absorbance measurements. A Cambridge pH meter (Bench model) was employed for all pH measurements, standardised at pH 4.0 and at pH 9.27.

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Reagents and Chemicals

Standard rhodium(III) solution: The standard solution was prepared by dissolving rhodium(III) chloride in dilute hydrochloric acid. The metal content of the solution was determined by precipitating the metal with formic acid. The precipitate was ignited to pure metal by heating in a current of hydrogen. For spectrophotometric determination, weaker solutions were prepared by proper dilution of the stock solution.

Diverse ion solutions: Solutions of diverse ions were prepared by dissolving known amounts of pure compounds in distilled water. Dilute hydrochloric acid was used where required.

Reagent solutions: 1% solution of PBT in 50% acetic acid solution was used for precipitation of rhodium(III). For spectrophotometric measurements, 0.01M reagent in ethanol was used.

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Gravimetric determination of rhodium

Procedure: Dilute a known amount of rhodium(III) solution to about 200 ml with distilled water in a beaker. Warm the solution to about 60°-70° and add slowly 3-4 times the theoretical amount of 1% PBT solution in 50% acetic acid with constant stirring. Adjust the pH of the solution to 3.5-5.5 by adding dropwise 4(N) ammonia solution with constant stirring. Place the beaker on a boiling water bath and digest the light yellow precipitate formed for 1-2 hr with occasional stirring. Filter the precipitate on a no. 4 sintered glass crucible. Wash the precipitate with 1% hot acetic acid solution. Dry

the complex at 110°–120° in an oven for 2 hrs, cool in a desiccator and weigh as $\text{Rh}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{OS})_3$. Calculate the metal content on the basis that the precipitate contained 11.82% of rhodium. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF RHODIUM

Rh-taken (mg)	Foreign ion added (mg)	Rh-found (mg)	Error (mg)
3.75	—	3.78	+0.03
7.14	—	7.12	-0.02
11.25	—	11.26	+0.02
7.51	$^a\text{Cu}^{2+}$ (150)	7.52	+0.01
7.51	$^b\text{Fe}^{3+}$ (150)	7.53	+0.02
7.51	$^c\text{Ni}^{2+}$ (200)	7.51	0.00
7.51	$^d\text{Hg}^{2+}$ (250)	7.52	+0.01
7.51	$^d\text{Ti}^{4+}$ (250)	7.51	0.00
7.51	$^e\text{Co}^{2+}$ (200)	7.52	+0.01
7.51	$^c\text{Mn}^{2+}$ (200)	7.50	-0.01
7.51	$^c\text{Ti}^{3+}$ (200)	7.51	0.00
7.51	$^c\text{Al}^{3+}$ (150)	7.51	0.00
7.51	$^c\text{Mo}^{6+}$ (150)	7.53	+0.02
7.51	$^c\text{W}^{6+}$ (200)	7.51	0.00
7.51	$^c\text{UO}_2^{2+}$ (300)	7.52	+0.01
7.51	$^c\text{Th}^{4+}$ (300)	7.49	-0.02
7.51	$^c\text{V}^{5+}$ (150)	7.51	0.00
7.51	$^c\text{Cd}^{2+}$ (300)	7.50	-0.01
7.51	$^c\text{Au}^{3+}$ (300)	7.52	+0.01
7.51	$^d\text{Pd}^{2+}$ (100)	7.51	0.00
7.51	$^d\text{Pt}^{4+}$ (90)	7.52	+0.01
7.51	$^d\text{Ir}^{4+}$ (150)	7.53	+0.02
7.51	$^d\text{Os}^{6+}$ (250)	7.51	0.00
7.51	$^d\text{Ru}^{3+}$ (250)	7.51	0.00

a = In presence of EDTA, b = In presence of fluoride;
 c = In presence of tartrate, d = In presence of sulphur dioxide,
 e = In presence of hydroxylamine hydrochloride.

The complete precipitation of the chelate took place in the pH range 3.5 to 5.5 when the supernatant liquid contained about 0.01% (w/v) of the reagent in excess, keeping the other conditions same.

Rhodium was determined with PBT in a mixture containing known amounts of diverse ions and the results are shown in Table 1. The metal was separated from the base metals using EDTA, tartrate or fluoride ions as masking agents. Rhodium was separated from palladium or platinum by precipitation of the latter with PBT in 0.5*N* hydrochloric acid medium. The metal was also precipitated with the reagent in presence of osmium(VI) and ruthenium(III) by prior reduction of the latter metal ions with sulphur dioxide and hydroxylamine hydrochloride respectively.

The rhodium complex is stable in dilute hydrochloric acid or sulphuric acid but decomposes in nitric acid. The chelate is soluble in chloroform, ethanol and partly soluble in benzene. The results of analysis of the pure complex, dried at 120°, are

as follows: Found: Rh = 11.80%; N = 14.40%; S = 11.00%. Required for $\text{Rh}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{OS})_3$: Rh = 11.82%; N = 14.46%; S = 11.02%.

Spectrophotometric determination of rhodium(III)

Procedure: In a 100 ml separatory funnel, introduce a measured amount of rhodium(III) solution and adjust the pH of the solution 5.24–6.3 by the addition of dilute hydrochloric acid and 10% sodium acetate solution. Mix the solution with an excess amount of 0.01*M* ethanolic solution of PBT by shaking vigorously and place the funnel with its contents over a boiling water bath for about 25–30 mins. Cool the separatory funnel to room temperature and shake the precipitate 2–3 times with 5 ml portions of chloroform followed by the addition of 5 ml of ethanol. Separate and dilute the yellowish brown complex extract into a 25 ml volumetric flask with chloroform. Dry over anhydrous sodium sulphate and measure the absorbance against reagent blank prepared under the same conditions with the same quantity of the reagent.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance curves of the extracts containing varying concentrations of rhodium ranging from 1.38 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ to 5.52 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ at pH 5.5 are shown in Fig. 1. The spectral absorbance of the complex was studied over the wavelengths ranging from 310 nm to 410 nm. The curves showed maximum absorbance at 340 nm. The extract of the complex obeyed Beer's law at 360 nm over the concentration range 0.69 $\mu\text{g Rh ml}^{-1}$ to 6.9 $\mu\text{g Rh ml}^{-1}$. Since the reagent has slight absorption at 340 nm, all the spectral measurements were made at 360 nm. The most suitable pH range for complete extraction of the rhodium chelate from aqueous phase was found to be 5.24 to 6.30 when the reagent concentration was ten times to that of rhodium(III) ion concentration.

The sensitivity of colour reaction and molar absorptivity of the rhodium chelate were calculated and found to be 0.0102 $\mu\text{g Rh cm}^{-2}$ and $9.54 \times 10^3 \text{ l.mole}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ at 360 nm respectively. The relative mean error and the coefficient of variation of the procedure were found to be 0.23% and 0.64% respectively.

Nature of the complex: The empirical formula of the rhodium(III)-PBT complex in ethanol-chloroform mixture was assigned by mole-ratio method as described by Meyer and Ayres⁹. The results, shown in Fig 2 clearly indicate that the stable complex was formed between the rhodium and *N*- α -pyridyl-*N'*-benzoyl thiourea in the ratio 1 : 3. The composition of Rh(III)-PBT complex was verified by conventional slope-ratio method.

The dissociation constant¹⁰ of the rhodium complex was determined from the mole-ratio curve and found to be 2.8×10^{-15} .

Effect of diverse ions: Rhodium(III) was separated and determined with PBT in presence of diverse ions

Fig. 1. Absorbance curves of Rhodium(III) N- α -Pyridyl-N' benzoyl thiourea, complex in ethanol-chloroform mixture A = 1.38 $\mu\text{g Rh ml}^{-1}$, B = 2.76 $\mu\text{g Rh ml}^{-1}$, C = 5.52 $\mu\text{g Rh ml}^{-1}$ $\bullet$ = 10 $^{-4}$ M reagent

Fig 2. Composition study by mole-ratio method applied to Rhodium(III) N- α Pyridyl-N' benzoyl thiourea complex in ethanol Chloroform mixture.

as described under the procedure. In the study of the effect of diverse ions, tartrate was added to prevent the hydrolysis or complex formation of some foreign ions. Interferences of copper, nickel, iron and mercury were avoided by masking with EDTA and of titanium with fluoride ions. Palladium(II) was removed by extraction with PBT in chloroform at room temperature in 0.1(N) hydrochloric acid. Rhodium was separated from platinum by the prior extraction of the latter with PBT in 0.5

(N) hydrochloric acid solution and the metal was determined in the aqueous layer after raising its pH to 5.5. Iridium(IV), osmium(IV) and ruthenium(II) did not interfere with the extraction and subsequent spectrophotometric determination of the metal with the chelating ligand. Cyanide ions, however, interfered. The tolerance limit for the foreign ions was taken as the largest amount which deviated the absorbance due to rhodium(III) by not more than 2 per cent. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS ON THE SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF RHODIUM(III)

Rhodium taken = 57.6 μg			
Foreign ion added	Amount tolerated (μg)	Foreign ion added	Amount tolerated (μg)
^a Fe ³⁺	2000	^b W ⁶⁺	2000
^a Cu ²⁺	2000	^b V ⁵⁺	1500
^a Ni ²⁺	2500	^b UO ²⁺	2000
^a Hg ²⁺	2000	^b Tl ³⁺	2000
^b Al ³⁺	2500	^b Pb ²⁺	2000
^b Co ²⁺	2500	^b Au ³⁺	2000
^c Ti ⁴⁺	2500	^b Pt ⁴⁺	2000
^b Cd ²⁺	3000	^b Pd ²⁺	3000
^b Mn ²⁺	3000	^a Os ⁶⁺	2000
^b Zn ²⁺	3000	^c Ru ³⁺	2000
^b Mo ⁶⁺	1500	^b Ir ⁴⁺	1000

a = In presence of EDTA, *b* = In presence of tartrate,
c = In presence of fluoride, *d* = In presence of sulphur dioxide,
e = In presence of hydroxylamine hydrochloride.

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